

CASE STUDY

CONGENITAL ABSENCE OF FEMUR IN OGHARA, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

OBJECTIVE : To highlight a rare congenital malformation in children

CASE REPORT :

A case report is that of a seven month old infant with congenital absence of left femur : a rare congenital malformation. Parents were puzzled at this “monstrous” deformity in a society where congenital dysmorphism is often explained by weird superstitions which may ultimately lead to parental child abandonment.

CONCLUSION : This case report highlights a rare congenital malformation. With increasing access of the general population to orthodox health institutions, many other rare congenital anomalies are bound to be reported from this part of the world.

KEYWORDS: Congenital, femur, absence, malformation

INTRODUCTION

Congenital malformation (dysmorphology) of different parts of the body is well known (Jones, 1996). However the absence of the femur is rare in which the femur being absent, the knee arises from the hip (Badoe *et al.*, 2000). The aetiology of musculoskeletal malformation is largely unknown but in the past, the role of thalidomide in association with limb abnormalities like phocomelia is well documented (Rang *et al.*, 1995). Certain limb abnormalities are associated with other conditions like thigh hemihypertrophy with Wilm’s tumour.

The aim of this report is to highlight this rather rare congenital anomaly as a congenital cause of leg length discrepancy in babies.

CASE REPORT

This seven month old boy presented to the general paediatric out patient clinic of the Delta State University Teaching Hospital, Oghara, Delta State of Nigeria. Besides the right limb shortening, the baby was normal in every respect since birth. He had normal developmental milestones for his age and there was no visceral congenital anomaly (Fig 1a & 1b).

DISCUSSION

Congenital anomaly of this rare type is bound to raise a lot of superstitious questions especially in the rural illiterates in Nigeria. In this case, the parents were wondering why the baby should be born with one limb shorter than the other. They seem not satisfied by whatever explanations the nurses and doctors they had met in the general hospitals had given them hence their presentation to the teaching hospital. During the clinical consultation section, the parents were educated about the congenital random nature of the anomaly and misgivings that the anomaly resulted from mistakes made by the midwife who performed the delivery were promptly dispelled.

CONCLUSION

Rare congenital anomalies like this should always be highlighted to buttress the fact that no geographical region of the world or race is immuned to these chance “accidents of nature” during foetal development. The challenge

is in health educating our rural illiterates and semi-illiterates on the pure medical reality of these anomalies rather than attributing them to superstitious conjectures.

Fig 1a: X-ray of the limb

Fig 1b: Picture of the baby

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